

Pathogen detection on microfluidic platforms: Recent advances, challenges, and prospects

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Point-of-care
Pathogen
Detection
LAMP
CRISPR
Microfluidics
Lab-on-chip

ABSTRACT

Point-Of-Care (POC) testing has advanced to more affordable and rapid alternatives by adapting conventional immunoassays and molecular assays (isothermal amplification, CRISPR, digital and real-time quantitative PCR) on polymeric and paper microfluidic platforms. However, commercialization of these POC devices often depends on tackling long-term challenges in performing conventional tests on novel platforms including contamination, assay sensitivity, accurate signal detection, minimizing manual handling, and instrumentation. This review presents recent advances in detection techniques (immunoassays and molecular assays on microfluidic platforms) and aids for improving detection throughput. Various prospects for sustainable pathogen detection and future developments for commercial viability in the field of rapid diagnostics are also discussed.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background & scope

Developing point of care (POC) testing has gained immense popularity over the past few years, with advanced molecular tests like digital amplification systems for a single copy of nucleic acid and CRISPR (Everitt et al., 2021; Lau et al., 2020; Niemz et al., 2011; Rezaei et al., 2021). This has generated much interest in assessing the feasibility of these methods on a suitable platform for large-scale and remote testing that allows for a sample-in-answer-out technology (Chu et al., 2021).

The WHO has described a POC diagnostic to be “affordable, sensitive, user-friendly, rapid and robust, equipment-free and deliverable to end-users” (Drain et al., 2014; Pai et al., 2015). Currently used techniques, such as PCR, ELISA, and other immunoassays, involve many sample preparation steps and are time-consuming (Espy et al., 2006; Mohit et al., 2021). These techniques need to be miniaturized and integrated into a single chip that can perform all the sample preparation steps, assay, detection, and analysis. Microfluidic-based POC devices, often also called lab-on-a-chip POC devices, overcome many challenges as

they are small, cost-effective, highly sensitive, accurate, and allow for the detection of multiple analytes in one sample (Foudeh et al., 2012; Lippa et al., 2011; Tak For Yu et al., 2015; Zanolli and Spoto, 2013).

Several recent reviews describe in detail the need for POC technologies with an emphasis on identifying how POC devices can assist in hospital environments and the economic benefits of miniaturization using microfluidic platforms for resource-limited settings (Drain et al., 2014; Li et al., 2020a; Lippa et al., 2011; Mejía-Salazar et al., 2020; Nasser et al., 2018; Tüdös et al., 2001; Zanolli and Spoto, 2013). Within the technology area, there have been considerable advancements in the sensors used in pathogen detection devices to achieve portability and make them compatible with smartphones, whereby analysis is combined with readout (da Silva et al., 2017; Zarei, 2017). The use of paper as a platform for POC devices for molecular and immunoassays has led to many reviews that compile these research outcomes and identify possible strategies for commercial use of paper-based assays (Carrell et al., 2019; Chinnadayala et al., 2019; Murray and Mace, 2020; Tavakoli et al., 2020; Zarei, 2018).

However, there are several knowledge gaps. Reviews that focus on POC technology have tended to focus on the overall technology for a broad range of uses including biomarker detection (Li et al., 2020a).

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Abbreviations:

AIV	Avian Influenza Virus
CRISPR	clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats
CFU	colony forming units
ELISA	enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
HRP	horseradish peroxidase
LAMP	isothermal loop-mediated amplification
LFA	lateral flow assay
LOC	lab-on-chip
LLOD	lower limit of detection
MBs	magnetic beads
PAM	protospacer adjacent motif
PMPs	superparamagnetic particles
POC	point of care
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
PDMS	poly-dimethylsiloxane
PMMA	poly-methylmethacrylate
RCA	rolling circle amplification
RPA	recombinase polymerase amplification

Some reviews focus on pathogen detection from food sources for food-borne diseases, which create significant differences in device design due to the nature of raw samples and contaminants (Cho and Ku, 2017; Fu et al., 2021; Kant et al., 2018). More recent reviews specific to pathogen detection on microfluidic devices focus on aspects of microchannel and substrates design but not on issues of molecular techniques and the detection process that hinder the commercialization of many academically developed devices (Carrell et al., 2019; Musile et al., 2021; Nasser et al., 2018; T. Nguyen et al., 2020; Qin et al., 2021). Therefore, this article aims to understand and organize the recent advances made in microfluidic-based POC devices for pathogen detection with a particular emphasis on common issues within assays, detection methods, and improving throughput. This includes developments made in various nucleic acid amplification and detection methods and the design of environments in which detection takes place. This review will outline the performance of novel methodologies, assessing possible limitations and use cases.

1.2. Challenges in traditional pathogen detection

Pathogens are disease-causing microorganisms that play a vital role in the health of humans, animals & plants, food safety, and environmental toxicity. Early detection of these microbes can be the key to preventing loss of life and resources and provide pathways for better policies on disease control in various industries (Alberts et al., 2002; Cho and Ku, 2017; Steele et al., 2016). Traditional pathogen detection methods may include bacterial cultures overnight on Petri dishes, automated systems (such as the BacTec system), and molecular methods such as PCR, and immunoassays (ELISA) for clinically relevant pathogens (Jung et al., 2015; Lau et al., 2020; Niemz et al., 2011; Zarei, 2018).

Compared to traditional plating methods (24–48 h for culture growth), immunoassays have a quicker turnaround time and can process many samples simultaneously. The methods are well established, versatile, and highly specific (targeted antigens) (Hosseini et al., 2018). Molecular methods rely on information preserved through genetic structures that often encode important proteins or other biomolecules, indicative of a specific nature of the disease. These are much faster than culture-based methods (real-time PCR has a turnaround time of 30 min to 2 h as compared to 24–48 h for plating methods). Molecular methods also are highly specific, sensitive towards low copy number plasmids, and versatile enough to be combined with other rapid methods or

multiplexed to create a reliable point-of-care test (Dong et al., 2008; Hoorfar et al., 2004; Kralik and Ricchi, 2017; Waliullah et al., 2019).

Recent advances in point-of-care tests on a microfluidic platform have garnered interest across industries and are referred to as lab-on-chip (LOC) devices (Li et al., 2020a; Mejia-Salazar et al., 2020; Nasser et al., 2018). A LOC device is an integrated device that can carry out measurements with extremely small sample volumes (Mark et al., 2010; Sin et al., 2011; Stone et al., 2004). The LOC pathogen sensing system for both molecular methods and immunoassays should be sensitive with a low limit of detection (LLOD), cost-effective, size-selective, simple to use, and have a large dynamic range (Drain et al., 2014; Henares et al., 2008; Mou and Jiang, 2017; Nasser et al., 2018; Zanolli and Spoto, 2013). The miniaturization of assays with LOC has significant advantages including the requirement for a small volume of reagents and solvents, low cost, portability, low power consumption, versatility in design, and potential for parallel operation and integration with other miniaturized devices (Mark et al., 2010; Sin et al., 2011; Stone et al., 2004). Selecting the most appropriate method to use on a microfluidic platform requires insight into the various challenges inherent in the particular assay, while also considering benefits and potential improvements (Table 1).

2. Pathogen detection on microfluidic systems

Microfluidic systems capture and leverage the behavior of a liquid or a gas in a very small volume (10^{-9} to 10^{-18} L) by controlling the flow using microchannels with dimensions of 10–100 μm in cross-section. There have been several improvements in microfluidic LOC systems including automation, increased efficiency, increased sensitivity, and broad analytical capabilities, leading to significant growth in diagnostics and other biological applications (Fig. 1) (Haeberle and Zengerle, 2007; Mark et al., 2010; Mou and Jiang, 2017; Ong et al., 2008; Stone et al., 2004).

For biological applications, it is imperative to consider bioaffinity and specificity while designing the microchannels and fabricating the chip, without losing assay performance during nucleic acid amplification and quantification of the biomarkers (Gomez, 2008; Haeberle and Zengerle, 2007; Henares et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2010a; Ong et al., 2008; Whale et al., 2012). The most common method to imprint microchannel designs and fabricate a microfluidic chip is soft lithography. To manufacture a working microfluidic chip, first, the design is finalized, after which the fabrication of microfluidic channels is done with or without a photomask. For LOC applications, various materials have been used as substrate material for biomarker detection including polymeric materials (PDMS (Polydimethyl siloxane), COC (Cyclic olefin copolymer), PMMA (Polymethyl methacrylate)), paper, glass, and silicon (Gravesen et al., 1993; Ong et al., 2008; Ren et al., 2013; Whitesides, 1998).

Although these materials can be used for microfluidic platforms, the different properties of these materials and associated fabrication processes affect the commercial preference. Recent advances in microfluidic systems have considered the advantage of combining more than one material to create novel microenvironments for increased biological applications (Dou et al., 2015; Raj M & Chakraborty, 2020). Specific to pathogen detection, microfluidic systems can be designed in a planar form ("microarray" configuration) where each microwell of the array acts as a reactor, or as a 3D bead-based system (Yeo et al., 2011). Bead-based systems improve the speed, flexibility, and detection limits of classic assays by immunocapture and magnetic separation to detect pathogens. Microfluidic systems incorporating magnetic particles can be applied in two unique ways (Haukanes and Kvam, 1993; Wu et al., 2020; Yeo et al., 2011):

- 1) sample preparation (preconcentration of relevant biomolecules such as peptides, DNA/RNA, etc.), or
- 2) direct biosensing by magnetic separation.

Table 1
Compatible and challenging aspects of traditional methods when adapting to lab-on-chip systems for pathogen detection.

Method	Compatible Aspects	Challenging Aspects	References
ELISA/Sandwich Immunoassay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible assay design • High sensitivity and specificity for established assays 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antibody cross-reactivity between detection and capture • Antibody can be common • Assay standardization required • Limited multiplexing options • High sample volumes • Tedious procedure (many steps) 	(Everitt et al., 2021; Hosseini et al., 2018; Sachdeva et al., 2021; Tanriverdi et al., 2010; Yin et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2019)
Quantitative PCR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low sample volumes • Sensitive and accurate quantified detection • Multiplexing is considerably easier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assay modification and extra steps required to quantify only viable nucleic acids • Primer design must be considered for high sensitivity and specificity • Thermocycler required (increased cost and device engineering) • Interference from nucleic acid extraction methods is possible 	
LAMP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low sample volumes • Highly rapid assay • Multiplexing is easier • No thermocycling is required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primer design for some isothermal methods (LAMP) require multiple considerations to ensure stability and specificity • Interference from nucleic acid extraction methods is possible 	
CRISPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very high single-base resolution for assay sensitivity • Instrument-free capacity • Can be stand-alone or integrated with amplification methods • Relatively tolerant to raw samples and lysed samples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement of PAM sequences that enhance sensitivity but limit target regions • Limited established strategies for multiplexed detection by CRISPR • Quantification is challenging due to the high sensitivity of the system and the limited reporter molecules • Standardization of assays required 	

Fig. 1. Timeline of significant landmarks in microfluidic-based pathogen detection (Chin et al., 2012; Convery and Gadegaard, 2019; Kim, 2013; Manmana et al., 2021; Manz et al., 1990; Sachdeva et al., 2021; Terry et al., 1979).

2.1. Immunoassay methods of pathogen detection

A typical immunoassay uses the sandwich configuration where two antibodies are used, which through a sequence of incubation and wash steps, allows the detection of the antigen (Alhajj and Farhana, 2021; Sakamoto et al., 2018). Immunoassays must leverage highly efficient biosensors for increased sensitivity and specificity of bioreceptors, reusability, and pH and temperature stability. There is an interest in microfluidic immunoassays as the protocol can be labor-intensive, time-consuming, and may need improved sensitivity (Asal et al., 2018; Chao et al., 2016; Chatterjee et al., 2022; Gu and Liu, 2020).

The problem of the time-consuming nature of conventional ELISA

was addressed by using a novel ZnO nanorod integrated microdevice as a multiplex immunofluorescence platform (Yu et al., 2017). The integrated microchip was used to capture AIV on the surface of immunologically functionalized ZnO nanorods and detection was achieved using a multiplexed sandwich immunoassay. The authors theorized that the high surface-to-volume ratio and intensified fluorescence of the ZnO nanostructure would improve the sensitivity while enhancing mixing by herringbone structures. Nonspecific adsorption was circumvented by fast continuous flow in the microchannels. The entire detection process was completed within 1.5 h, and the LLOD was measured as 3.6×10^3 EID50 mL⁻¹. The authors acknowledge that, despite lower sensitivity than molecular assays like rRT-PCR, immunoassays are a practical

application for pathogen detection due to their flexibility (i.e., easily customizable assays for a specific pathogen) and portability (Yu et al., 2017).

Recently, assay sensitivity has been improved by using electrowetting-on-dielectric (EWOD) based digital microfluidics to detect pathogens (Coudron et al., 2019). The assay was performed by selective capture of the antigen by antibody-coated magnetic beads (for sample volumes as low as 2.5 μL), followed by adding a secondary antibody for detection and measuring the emitted light intensity. The luminescent droplet was subsequently moved by EWOD to the photodetector for light collection. Here, the reported EWOD-based aerosol sampling systems improved the concentration of small volume droplets with the lower limits of detection of Human Serum Albumin, *Bacillus atrophaeus*, MS₂ bacteriophage, and *Escherichia coli* of 30 ng mL⁻¹, 4 \times 10⁴ CFU mL⁻¹, 10⁶ CFU mL⁻¹, and 2 \times 10⁷ CFU mL⁻¹ respectively. The detection system was able to generate results within 10 min (Coudron et al., 2019).

Although enzyme-substrate reactions enjoy the advantage of being easily detectable (Gu and Liu, 2020; Hosseini et al., 2018; Pruslin et al., 1991), drawbacks include high costs due to difficulty in production and interference with samples (Asal et al., 2018; Chatterjee et al., 2022; Gu and Liu, 2020; Sakamoto et al., 2018). In recent years, label-free detection methods, including surface plasmon resonance have been applied widely for pathogen detection (Lee et al., 2013; Mariani and Minunni, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2015; Skottrup et al., 2007; Wang and Park, 2020). Detection methods based on the labeling of gold nanoparticles (colorimetric detection) (Jung et al., 2010; Peng and Chen, 2018; Verma et al., 2015) and magnetic microbeads (magnetolectric detection) (Charlarmroj et al., 2013; Gheorghiu, 2021; Kim et al., 2010b) have been studied extensively. A novel nonenzymatic surface plasmon resonance (SPR) biosensor to detect multiple pathogenic bacteria was demonstrated by combining autocatalytic multi-component DNA-based enzymes (short synthetic oligonucleotides with catalytic activity) integrated with SPR to allow cleavage on magnetic beads (Xia et al., 2021). As the number of cleaved DNA segments increased, the SPR signal from the analyte was also enhanced. The detection limits using this system were found to be 67 CFU mL⁻¹ of *S. aureus*, 57 CFU mL⁻¹ of *K. pneumoniae*, and 61 CFU mL⁻¹ of *E. coli*. Alternatively, an SPR-based sensor was developed by functionalizing the sensors with polyclonal antibodies raised against *C. jejuni* using covalent attachment which were directly detected by gold chips (Masdor et al., 2017). The sensitivity was enhanced to 4 \times 10⁴ CFU mL⁻¹, which is better than that of commercial ELIA (10⁶–10⁷ CFU mL⁻¹).

A fully automated microfluidic-based electrochemical biosensor was

developed (Altintas et al., 2018) by having the key features of an integrated microfluidic system, the biochip design, and real-time amperometric measurements (Fig. 2). The antibodies were added to a buffer solution containing gold nanoparticles, allowing adsorption on the AuNP surface at their isoelectric point due to electrostatic interactions. The detection of *E. coli* was then investigated after immobilizing the primary *E. coli* antibody onto electrode surfaces. Better detection limits were achieved with this nanoparticle-modified immunoassay (50 CFU mL⁻¹) as compared to conventional immunoassays for *E. coli* detection (1.99 \times 10⁴ CFU mL⁻¹).

It is also possible to combine the use of magnetic particles with a direct sensing method like flow cytometry for improved specificity in detection. A novel strategy to detect *S. aureus* was developed by using bovine serum albumin (BSA) as the amplification carrier to modify magnetic beads (MBs) functionalized with vancomycin (a Gram-positive specific antibiotic) (Meng et al., 2017). To detect the signal, the authors tagged pig immunoglobulin G with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC-pig IgG) to create the signal probe on the surface of *S. aureus*. By measuring the fluorescence signal by flow cytometry, the actual concentration of *S. aureus* could be quantified. The use of multivalent magnetic nanoprobes (Van-BSA-MBs) was reported to detect a lower limit of 33 CFU mL⁻¹ within 120 min. Other advantages with this sandwich mode (FITC-pig IgG/SA/Van-BSA-MBs) included higher specificity, improved pathogen capture efficiency, and decreased nonspecific adsorption showing potential use in clinical settings.

2.2. Molecular methods of pathogen detection

2.2.1. Isothermal amplification

The loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology is an emerging isothermal nucleic acid amplification method developed by Notomi et al. (2000). The basic principle of LAMP is auto-cycling strand displacement DNA synthesis in the presence of enzyme Bst DNA polymerase. The reaction has a turnaround time of 30–60 min under isothermal conditions between 60 and 65 °C (Nagamine et al., 2002; Notomi et al., 2000). Other isothermal amplification techniques have also been explored for pathogen detection including nucleic acid sequence-based amplification (Abdolazadeh et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2017; Yue et al., 2019), rolling circle amplification (Ciftci et al., 2019; Ma, Chen, et al., 2019; Soares et al., 2019), strand displacement amplification (Ngamdee et al., 2020; Phillips et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021), helicase dependent amplification (Kolm et al., 2019; Tupik et al., 2018) and single primer isothermal amplification (Kumar et al., 2018). While these methods have some advantages, there are more

Fig. 2. Custom-designed electrochemical biosensor for *E. coli* detection (Altintas et al., 2018).

shortcomings to overcome, such as nonspecific amplifications causing high background noise, primer design criteria, and low tolerances to raw samples needing highly optimized reaction systems. In contrast, LAMP is faster and more stable, sensitive, and specific for nucleic acid detection. It also can amplify a medium to a long range of nucleic acids, which makes it suitable for detecting various DNA or RNA sequences (Seki et al., 2018; Silva Zatti et al., 2020).

Over the last decade, tremendous attention has been given to developing microfluidic devices that can efficiently perform various isothermal amplification reactions (Ma, Chen, et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2020; Soares et al., 2019; Tupik et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021; Zanoli and Spoto, 2013). Isothermal amplification techniques not only differ in the mechanism of the assay but also are unique to the type of nucleic acid under study (ssDNA, dsDNA, or RNA) in terms of reaction conditions (temperature, enzymes involved, and reaction time). The most common bottlenecks to commercializing microfluidic LAMP devices are contamination issues, maintaining the stability of LAMP reagents such as primers, and the ability to multiplex reactions to improve throughput (Shang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019), which has led to the emergence of novel strategies (Fig. 3).

A possible solution to dealing with cross-contamination in LAMP assays is improving sealed systems for trapping amplicons (Karthik et al., 2014) or using a storage matrix to carry out LAMP assays (Chen et al., 2017). A microfluidic in-gel loop-mediated isothermal amplification (gLAMP) system was developed containing preloaded reagents as a self-contained microdevice. The microchannel dimensions in the gLAMP microchip were optimized for loading LAMP reagents into the device by negative pressure after the device was degassed. A low melting point agarose solution with LAMP reagents and the sample would occupy the microchannels in the chip. As agarose does not contribute to background fluorescence and is biocompatible, LAMP-in-gel systems are promising for quantitative, multiplexed POC devices. The authors found the LLOD to be 3 copies/uL and no cross-contamination was observed, although the shelf life of this device was found to be only 30 days at 4 °C. Another approach to prevent aerosol-based contamination is trapping the amplicons within a hydrophobic liquid. Droplet-based microfluidic

systems address the low throughput nature of conventional amplification methods by compartmentalizing reaction mixes in $\sim 10^4 - 10^6$ water in oil microdroplets; however, each drop needs to be examined individually for a signal (Jiang et al., 2016). This was addressed by combining LAMP-in-a-drop with a mathematical model that predicts a positive signal, to minimize detection time (Azizi et al., 2019). The method relies on confining the mixture of the LAMP reaction cocktail and the extracted RNA from targeted bacteria within small water-in-oil microdroplets on a PDMS chip. While the obtained detection limit is comparable, the authors observe that the model can only predict the probability of a positive droplet vs negative, and more computing is required to determine the concentration of product in each droplet. A more practical approach of circumventing contamination was designed by minimizing pipetting steps within disposable chips (Zhong et al., 2020). The authors stated that their prototype has overcome the LAMP contamination issue by using a dedicated plastic shell for assembling the chip and completely sealing the LAMP system to minimize the risk of amplicon escape (Fig. 3(C)). They employed a thermoelectric cooler (TEC)-based temperature-control module and a CCD-based fluorescence imaging module for real-time detection of LAMP results. The authors focused on the design and chip fabrication to allow balance in functionality (no extra device for assay or detection), throughput (4 samples per chip for two primers), and cost.

Hybrid POC devices using paper/polymer provide the advantages of longer shelf life and stability of reagents, capillary fluid transport (no external pneumatic pumps or electric power), with the transparent optical properties of polymer, making it ideal for disposable equipment-free testing (Carrell et al., 2019; Dou et al., 2014, 2015; Tavakoli et al., 2020). Dou et al. (2019) developed a low-cost hybrid microfluidic platform integrated with LAMP for rapid and instrument-free detection of whooping cough. A PDMS/paper hybrid chip was used for carrying out the assay by using the paper disk as a zone for carrying out LAMP reaction, while the transparent PDMS layer was used for manipulating flow within the channels.

The LAMP amplified product detection can be captured by analyzing at the end-point or real-time monitoring (Table 2).

Fig. 3. Microfluidic systems to combat assay contamination during LAMP (A) Schematic of the microfluidic flow-focusing device LAMP reaction in water-in-oil droplets and fluorescent detection (Azizi et al., 2019) (B) Microchip preparation and in-gel LAMP operation (Chen et al., 2017) (C) Microfluidic chip with diffusion-free filling of the reaction wells from a single pipetting step in less than 10 s and complete sealing of the chip with a plastic shell (Zhong et al., 2020).

Table 2
Detection methods of LAMP amplicons and their principles.

End-Point Detection	
Turbidity	Pyrophosphate ions released from dNTPs during the LAMP process react with magnesium ions to yield a white magnesium pyrophosphate precipitate ($Mg_2P_2O_7$) which increases the turbidity to be visualized with the naked eye (or turbidimeter) (Mori et al., 2001)
Colorimetric/Dye-based	Hydroxynaphthol blue (HNB) and calcein act by binding to Mg^{2+} to enhance fluorescence, while ethidium bromide, propidium iodide, SYBR Green I, and SYTO-81 intercalate between the strands of the newly formed ds-DNA to create a visible dye-dsDNA complex (Becherer et al., 2020; Fischbach et al., 2015).
Immunoassay	Lateral flow assays and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) can be used for detecting LAMP products by direct incorporation of labeled nucleotides in amplicons during the LAMP-amplification process and hybridization to specific captured oligonucleotide probes, finally, detection of the captured amplicons by immunoassay technology. (Lee et al., 2014; Ravan and Yazdanparast, 2012).

One of the complexities in observing the results of the LAMP assay is the requirement of a fluorescent probe or the addition of expensive dyes (Hardinge and Murray, 2019; Wong et al., 2018). Several recent reviews cover the mechanism, advantages and commercial viability of novel end point detection methods including electrochemical sensors, impedimetric sensors, surface plasmon resonance using modified gold nanoparticles and lateral flow colorimetric detection (Becherer et al., 2020; Glöckler et al., 2021; Pumford et al., 2020; Safavieh et al., 2016; Shen et al., 2020).

There are, however, considerable challenges to be faced before POC devices become routine in clinical practice including the integration of detection components with other fluid regulatory elements at the microscale and the development of new materials for environmentally friendly, cheap, and portable microfluidic devices.

2.2.2. CRISPR-assisted methods

Discovered in the 1980s, CRISPR (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats) is a family of DNA sequences found in prokaryotes and was initially used as a genome editing technique and eventually spread out to other applications due to its versatility and reliability. CRISPR-Cas systems have been developed for the detection of nucleic acids and biomarkers from pathogens, aiding the development of low-cost, sensitive, specific diagnostics for infectious diseases. The flexibility of CRISPR-based diagnostic devices can be attributed to targeting any nucleic acid sequence by changing the guide RNA sequence. Specific assays to detect low copy number genes have been developed which combine CRISPR specific cleavage and PCR amplification of target DNA, and then the results can be visualized with gel electrophoresis readout or qPCR (Sashital, 2018).

Yin et al. (2020) have reviewed the recent advances in viral detection using CRISPR-Cas for point-of-care applications mainly on lateral flow assay systems (Yin et al., 2021). Clinically significant POC systems using lateral flow assays included the detection of Zika and Dengue using SHERLOCK-LFA POC system and SARS-CoV-2 using CRISPR-Cas13 coupled with LFA (Patchsung et al., 2020). Other viruses that could be detected by combining CRISPR and LFA technologies included African swine fever virus (ASFV) (X. Wang et al., 2020), HPV 16 and HPV 18 (Mukama et al., 2020) and Epstein-Barr Virus (Yuan et al., 2020). Here, they have covered important challenges to CRISPR technologies which include sequence limitation (fewer choices in the target recognition region for cleavage due to requirement of PAM sequences), multiplexing and quantification, standardization, sample pre-treatment, contamination, and background noise (non-specific activation of Cas proteins) and challenges to field deployment (design of chip for field testing, storage requirements for stability of reagents).

The challenge in CRISPR is to develop a highly sensitive assay with or

without nucleic acid amplification. Qin et al. (2019) reported an automated POC system that allows multiple samples and quantified results for Ebola RNA detection. To improve sensitivity without amplification, the authors combined an automated and multiplexing CRISPR microfluidic chip with a benchtop fluorometer (also measures nonspecific cleavage products) for a minimum of ~ 10 μ L Ebola virus detection. The turnaround time for viral detection is less than 5 min, with a detection limit of 20 pfu/mL (5.45×10^7 copies/mL) of purified Ebola RNA. The authors built their microfluidic device to run 24 assays in parallel, as controlled by eight pneumatic inlets (Fig. 4) and note possible integration with a sample extraction system.

Ramachandran et al. (2020) combined microfluidics, on-chip electric field control, and CRISPR to detect SARS-CoV-2 while addressing limitations of current CRISPR-based diagnostic methods, including pre-extracted nucleic acids and manual steps of incubation and reagent addition. They leveraged the use of an electric field gradient to co-focus Cas12-gRNA, reporters, and target within a microfluidic chip to improve the assay efficiency and control. An electric field gradient was set up using isotachopheresis (ITP) implemented on a microfluidic chip by employing a two-buffer system consisting of a high-mobility leading electrolyte and a low-mobility trailing electrolyte buffer. The clinical validation of the assay was done against RT-PCR, with an LLOD of around 10 copies/ μ L which was noted to be slightly higher than the RT-PCR. However, the sample extraction/purification was combined with LAMP and the ITP-enhanced CRISPR assay allowed a turnaround time of 35 min. The authors note a disadvantage of intermediate off-chip manual steps.

Hass et al. (2020) demonstrated an integrated PDMS-CRISPR system for automated viral DNA sensing. The microfluidic chip was patterned with high aspect-ratio micropillars to enhance reporter probe binding. After surface modification (treatment with APTES) and probe immobilization (biotin-labeled DNA binding on the streptavidin-coated PDMS surface), the CRISPRCas12a/crRNA complex was injected into the fully enclosed microchannel. With the presence of a double-stranded DNA target, the CRISPR enzyme was activated and denatures the ssDNA reporters from the micropillars. This collateral cleavage releases fluorescence reporters into the assay, and the intensity was found to be linearly proportional to the target DNA concentration ranging from 0.1 to 10 nmol. As this system does not rely on the traditional dye-quencher-labeled probe, the challenge of fluorescence background noise was reduced. The detection protocol was performed on-chip at isothermal conditions (37 °C) without using complicated and time-consuming off-chip probe hybridization and denaturation. This miniaturized chip demonstrated DNA detection within 120 min and provides a good design strategy for noise-producing CRISPR assays.

CRISPR, both on its own and as a complementary detection method to amplification, greatly improves upon existing diagnostic solutions and achieves assay sensitivity that is clinically significant for the rapid diagnosis of disease. However, future deployment of CRISPR as a qualified diagnostic method depends on the performance of the assay after integration with other crucial steps, such as the sample preparation unit. It is also yet to be determined how CRISPR can be effective as a tool under field conditions that cannot meet laboratory settings and how long-term stability issues of RNA detection systems would be overcome (Lau et al., 2020; Sashital, 2018).

2.2.3. PCR

The molecular amplification technique of real-time PCR is the same as the polymerase chain reaction where a nucleic acid polymerase enzyme catalyzes the formation of products in the presence of sequence-specific oligonucleotides called primers, dNTPs (the building blocks for new products), Mg^{2+} , and buffers in a thermocycler. Real-time PCR or qPCR builds on top of the classic PCR by monitoring the accumulation of amplicons in “real-time” by measuring the change in emission of fluorescence (Apte and Daniel, 2009; Dieffenbach et al., 1993; Hoorfar et al., 2004; Kralik and Ricchi, 2017; Löfström et al., 2015) while microfluidic

Fig. 4. Improving CRISPR sensitivity: (A) An automated and multiplexing CRISPR microfluidic chip with a benchtop fluorometer for Ebola virus detection (Qin et al., 2019). (B) Integrated electric field-mediated microfluidic assay with nucleic acid extraction by isotachophoresis and RT-LAMP for CRISPR detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA detection (Ramachandran et al., 2020) (C) Automated viral-DNA sensing microfluidic chip with streptavidin coated PDMS surface and APTES-modified micropillars for isothermal detection (Hass et al., 2020).

digital PCR (dPCR) isolates single molecules by dilution and individually amplifying and analyzing them (Vogelstein and Kinzler, 1999). On a microfluidic platform, dPCR can be achieved by partitioning a sample before PCR amplification such that each reaction chamber contains 0 or ≥ 1 copy of target DNA and has the advantages of reduced background signal and increasing the signal-to-noise ratio of low-abundance targets (Sanders et al., 2011).

Microfluidic PCR systems are developed using polymer chips with specific functional domains for performing PCR and can be classified into three categories:

- (i) stationary-chamber micro PCR-chips as nano/picoliter reservoir for conventional thermocycling (Chang et al., 2006; Chen et al., 2007; Zhang and Ozdemir, 2009),
- (ii) continuous-flow micro-PCR chips where different temperature zones are established at different locations and the sample is moved between individual temperature zones for cycling (Jiang et al., 2014; Kulkarni and Goel, 2020; Li et al., 2019, 2020b; Mohammed et al., 2012) and
- (iii) droplet-based PCR systems where amplification reactions are conducted in water-in-oil droplets for each amplicon (Azizi et al., 2019; Sánchez Barea et al., 2019; Sohrabi and Moraveji, 2020; Wang and Burns, 2009; Y. Wang et al., 2020).

A general problem found with microfluidic devices is nonspecific adsorption due to the large surface-to-volume ratios present in microchannels, which are known to inhibit PCR reactions. However, a variety

of specific surface modification procedures using buffers like Triton-X or bulk modification methods for polymers have been implemented recently to overcome this limitation. Another major challenge involving non-specific primer interactions is the difficulty in multiplexing detection. One possible solution that is studied widely is designing the PCR chip with reaction chambers to incorporate lyophilized or pre-loaded primers to solve the two problems presented, namely, multiplexing and non-specific primer interactions (Jiang et al., 2014; Kulkarni and Goel, 2020; Li et al., 2019, 2020b; Wang and Burns, 2009; Zhang and Jiang, 2016). Due to rapid heating and cooling cycles being required to conduct a polymerase chain reaction, there is typically evaporative loss in the reaction mix, which leads to inaccurate results (Polini et al., 2010). In the conventional PCR thermocycler machine, the PCR tubes are provided with a cap seal to tightly hold the contents of the tube, and the assay is modified to accommodate this loss. However, in a microfluidic system, this could be a design challenge. Here, a hydrophobic liquid such as mineral or silicone oil needs to be added to prevent the evaporative loss, as well as mechanical sealing of the ports to prevent leakage (Polini et al., 2010; Zhang and Xing, 2007). Several new studies have emerged studying these challenges to provide sustainable one-device solutions to Real-Time PCR as a point-of-care diagnostic (Fig. 5).

To address the issue of rapid and instrument-free detection of respiratory pathogens Huang et al. (2021) developed a microfluidic chip-based PCR-array system (Onestart), with all the reagents needed for the pathogen detection assay being preloaded on the Onestart microfluidic chip to minimize mishandling. The LLOD of the Onestart assay

Fig. 5. Rapid and instrument-free PCR systems: (A) OneStart sample-in-answer-out system that combines nucleic acid extraction, real time PCR and fluorescent detection (Huang et al., 2021) (B) Integrated system with blister pouch cartridge create a disposable, easy-to-use device (Brennan et al., 2021) (C) Single step-microfluidic array-based PCR system with glass layers to prevent evaporative loss and bubble generation (Gorgannezhad et al., 2019).

was determined to be 1.0×10^3 copies mL^{-1} while the system to detect 21 clinically significant respiratory pathogens with 100% specificity, showing array-based detection systems are ideal for multiplexing applications. Gorgannezhad et al. (2019) have also developed a single step-microfluidic array-based PCR system to detect waterborne bacteria. There, the PCR solution was loaded into the array of reactors in a single step by means of capillary filling, thereby eliminating the need for pumps, valves, and liquid handling instruments. The LLOD was estimated to be 71.8 copies/mL. The authors recognized the various challenges in traditional and miniaturized PCR, including evaporative loss and bubble generation leading to loss of PCR efficiency. This was overcome by designing the chip with glass on the top and at the bottom of the PDMS layer, and oil on both sides of the microreactors, to capture the PCR sample and prevent its movement.

Cartridge-based systems that can hold lyophilized reagents have also been examined for point-of-care applications due to their ease of use and disposable nature. Brennan et al. (2021) demonstrate the use of a disposable cartridge system to screen *Chlamydia trachomatis* directly from urine samples. Inhibition of PCR reaction was overcome by the use of an internal control. Heating and liquid manipulation was achieved using pinch valves and a compressible blister pouch. The developed system was validated against the ABBOTT real-time PCR Cobas CT/NG test on 207 clinical samples demonstrating 81% sensitivity and 88% specificity.

3. Multiplexed pathogen detection

The detection of multiple pathogens from the same clinical specimen is an important advantage to improving diagnosis and therapeutic routes, especially in cases where many infections can be present simultaneously (e.g., TB and HIV (Friedland et al., 2007); Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C with HIV (Coffin et al., 2010; Lacombe and Rockstroh, 2012); SARS-CoV-2 with CMV in renal transplant patients (Shaikh et al., 2021)). Multiplex testing of several targets is possible by providing independent parallel reactors on a single chip, in which case a sample is divided and loaded into individual chambers. The different primers required for parallel detection are either dried in the individual chambers or are provided as part of the mastermix for multiplexed detection

(Liu et al., 2011; Mauk et al., 2015). The biggest challenge to successful multiplexing is ensuring the primers are specific and no cross-contamination takes place within the chip.

One of the easiest ways to optimize and perform multiplexed detection is to design the microfluidic chip to accommodate multiple channels as shown in Fig. 6. J. Yin et al. (2020) report a digital microfluidic chip using RPA for detection and divide the chamber into four parts, comprising of separate inlets (for individual reaction components), including one negative control area and three positive detection areas. Four different pathogens could be detected on their chip with high accuracy within 45 min. Sun et al. (2020) were able to detect five pathogens on a single chip using digital LAMP by drying and reconstituting the specific primers into solution during the addition of LAMP reaction mix. After deposition of specific primers, the channels were covered with a layer of double-sided adhesive and sealed by a piece of cover glass after sample injection to prevent sample evaporation; detection took place within 30 min, with a lower limit of 18 copies per reaction. Dou et al. (2017) developed a PMMA/paper hybrid, SpinChip, a rotary microfluidic device designed in a CD-like rotary format to facilitate the integration of both multiplexed LAMP reactions and nanosensor qLAMP detection. There, the rotary disk consists of a top PMMA plate that can be rotated to align the inlet for adding reagents. The bottom is the multiplex LAMP zone, which can be sealed tight by manually screwing the top. Due to the wicking effect of the paper, the system ensures the even distribution of LAMP products to the detection zones without pneumatic assistance. The authors state that 12 samples can be tested on the chip and that this can be scaled further.

The methods mentioned above are based on geometric modifications in chip design, which is a common approach to expand single to multiplexing (Mitchell et al., 2021). Modifications in chip design mainly consist of (1) expansion of chip layer or surface area per layer, (2) addition of on-chip structures including inlets/outlets, flow channels and reaction/detection chambers, and (3) arrangement of these structures within a limited area. Fabrication of microfluidic chips, irrespective of multiplex-friendly design, suffers from difficulties including complexity of chip integration, long development period, various techniques involved in manufacturing process and high cost, especially when the microfluidic chips are being prototyped for future

Fig. 6. Designs to incorporate multiplexed pathogen detection: (A) Hybrid rotary device with different functions for PMMA plate (Inlet delivery) and paper (LAMP zone) (Dou et al., 2017) (B) Designated channels for each primer set and controls (Sun et al., 2020) (C) Separated inlets for lyophilized components (J. Yin et al., 2020).

commercialization (Cong and Zhang, 2022).

The setup of the detection system plays an important role in ensuring the multiplexing capability of the platform. Fluorescence detection is now used more widely in microfluidics compared with colorimetry or electrochemical measurement (Basha et al., 2017). If multiplexing involves parallel reactions within the same chamber using specific primers in the mastermix, chip design can be kept simple while the detection module requires further consideration for accommodating multiple target wavelengths. For multiplexed pathogen detection inside one chamber (Geetha et al., 2020) or one droplet in droplet microfluidic systems (Xiao et al., 2019), the detection system requires more excitation channels, and even more detectors, e.g. photodiode, CCD or photomultiplier tube (PMT), to differentiate the pathogens and capture fluorescence signals with different wavelengths. Expansion of excitation channels is usually achieved by adding more light sources, e.g. LED and laser (Yun et al., 2021) or band pass filters after a broad-spectrum white light to provide excitation energy of distinct spectra. Other encoding tools like multi-color quantum dots (Ye et al., 2020) and photonic crystal beads (Yuan et al., 2014) may improve detection specificity and sensitivity for multiplexed pathogen detection through cost effectiveness and ease of automation.

4. Smart detection of pathogens

As an estimated 80.69% of the world's population owned a mobile phone in 2021 (O'Dea, 2021), there is an exponential increase in smartphones that have advanced computing capability, high-resolution image capture and processing (via a built-in smartphone camera), and an open-source operating system, which not only aids the development of low-cost POC devices but also provides remote analysis of assays, easy data storage, and records for further investigation. Many reviews have been published that report the recent advances in microfluidics combined with smartphone-based platforms (Ding et al., 2019; Nasseri et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2014). Smartphone accessories can be integrated with a microfluidic device in several ways depending on the nature of analytes:

1) an imaging biosensor (built-in high pixel Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) image sensor (CIS) camera records and quantifies morphological features such as object size, shape, brightness, or color),

- 2) a biochemical sensor (electrochemical amperometric biosensors usually constructed by chronoamperometry (CA), cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and square wave voltammetry can use the micro-USB port on a smartphone as the electronic interface between the miniaturized amperometric system and the smartphone for data upload),
- 3) molecular sensors to detect nucleic acids or other biomolecules (multifunctional uses for smartphones including power supply, endpoint detection, processor, or transducer)

As this review is concerned with pathogen sensing systems, a relevant use of integrating smartphones with microfluidic systems is in endpoint detection. According to the types of signals, smartphone-based endpoint optical detection has been reported based on color change, reflection, light emission, turbidity, or fluorescence intensity and the working of these detection methods are represented in Fig. 7. Ma, Li, et al. (2019) have reported an automated and portable microfluidic-based system that provided results in 40 min and was performed with a punching-press mechanism that could be controlled and monitored by a smartphone. The authors noted that purple-to-blue color changes only appeared in the positive controls and samples with concentrations higher than 3.2×10^{-3} HAU per reaction for H1N1 viruses (haemagglutinin units) or 30 CFU mL⁻¹ for MRSA, determined to be the LLOD, were consistent with the optical signals from the color sensor. In this integrated system, the smartphone fulfilled two roles: remote process automation and endpoint signal detection, thus proving that automated POC systems can be miniaturized without the need for bulky, laptop or PC processing systems. One of the major challenges in smartphone-based endpoint detection is to increase the accuracy of quantification from colorimetric detection methods while keeping the POC device resource-friendly. By placing a polarizer pair close to the smartphone camera, the signal-to-noise ratio improved to resolve the change in gray-value due to the colorimetric reaction up to 1:100 dilution. The smartphone-based detection limit was determined to be 8×10^3 EID₅₀/mL for the selective sensing of avian influenza virus (Xia et al., 2019).

Smartphones can also be used to heat the diagnostic assay, as demonstrated by H.V. Nguyen et al. (2020) who developed an integrated smartphone-based genetic analyzer which comprised of a smartphone and an integrated genetic analysis unit (i-Gene) in which the power of the smartphone was used for heating the amplification reaction, and the

Fig. 7. Smart-phone based colorimetric detection of pathogens: (A) and (B) Integrated portable diagnostic devices (Ma, Li, et al., 2019; H. V. Nguyen et al., 2020); (C) real-time color sensing using hue values (K. Yin et al., 2020). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

camera function was used for imaging the colorimetric change of the reaction. The controller-embedded film heater was powered by a 5.0 V power bank to maintain 63 °C for the LAMP reaction. On amplification, the blue-to-violet change was monitored real-time by the smartphone's complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor camera. The quantitative LAMP profiles were obtained by plotting the ratio of green/red intensity versus the reaction time and the authors were able to identify *E. coli* O157:H7 with a limit of detection of 101 copies/ μ L within 60 min. To improve and enable sensitive and quantitative molecular detection, Yin et al. (K. Yin et al., 2020) developed a portable platform which was built to include:

- 1) a portable processor which provided heat for LAMP,
- 2) a disposable microfluidic chip for nucleic acid extraction and LAMP, and
- 3) a programmed smartphone for real-time hue-based quantitative molecular detection.

To prove the concept, the authors quantitatively detected HPV in saliva samples/clinical vaginal swab samples and HIV in plasma with a limit of detection of 100 RNA copies and a total turnaround time of 1 h. The quantitative test results were also recorded by the smartphone and wirelessly transmitted to a website, together with the testing time and GPS coordinates, allowing real-time pathogen tracking and disease mapping.

Several recent reviews have described the advances and bottlenecks in automated microfluidic smartphone-based biosensors (Li et al., 2021b; Liu et al., 2019; Mejía-Salazar et al., 2020; Rajendran et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2018). The challenges in the integration and design of the smartphone-based microfluidic biosensor systems can be summarized as balancing the number of detection components attached to the smartphone and obtaining the target accuracy from the sensing system (Li et al., 2021b; Xu et al., 2018). It was noted that accessories affect the convenience and flexibility and interfere in the diagnostic process leading to loss of accuracy, while miniaturized sensors might not achieve accuracies comparable to conventional lab-setting analyzing instruments (Xu et al., 2018).

5. Conclusions and future prospects

The current outbreak of Covid-19 worldwide has exposed our deficiencies in the prevention and control of infectious diseases, especially in the aspects of rapid detection and early screening, which urgently require portable POC diagnostics and correlated devices to contribute to rapid and accurate detection of infections (Everitt et al., 2021; Rezaei et al., 2021). The selection of an amplification method for such a system comes with recognizing the inherent assay challenges (Table 1) and performance constraints including i) the sensitivity required from the assay, ii) design challenges in the microfluidic environment, iii) reagent storage, iv) preventing contamination, and v) commercial resources. Where resources are limited and constrained, isothermal methods are the most advantageous, due to their flexibility (assay cartridge can be heated on a thermal block or water bath), and the ease with which they can be integrated with sample treatment or allow direct detection from crude samples for the application of routine clinical diagnostics, particularly when the major challenge is risk of contamination (Wang et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2018; Zanoli and Spoto, 2013). Digital PCR, although reliable, easier to standardize and evaluate, has low tolerance for impure samples, is often time consuming, and requires a thermocycler which is expensive for resource limited settings (Kulkarni and Goel, 2020; T. Nguyen et al., 2020). When considering dPCR, the integrated performance of nucleic acid purification with fluorescent detection is key to commercialization (Everitt et al., 2021). For low copy number and nucleotide-scale detection, CRISPR-Cas systems prove more effective and offer potential as a future companion diagnostic with increasing clinical trial validation for commercial use (van Dongen et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2020).

Recent developments have shown an increase in employing isothermal amplification techniques like LAMP, RCA, and RPA for multiplexed pathogen detection using a single temperature for amplification, high versatility in assay design, high sensitivity especially LAMP, and a sustainable alternative to conventional PCR (Charlarmroj et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2017; Dou et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2010b; Zhao et al., 2015; Zhong et al., 2020). Different approaches could be employed to circumvent contamination issues, such as droplet-based microfluidic systems by sealing individual drops in oil (Sánchez Barea et al., 2019; Y. Wang et al., 2020) or designing the amplification chamber to be

completely sealed to minimize amplicon escape (Zhong et al., 2020). To counter the difficulty in storing reagents and maintaining the stability of the mix, progress in the use of polymer/paper hybrid environments has shown the ability of paper to hold reagents in a dried form for a long period (Carrell et al., 2019; Dou et al., 2014, 2015, 2017; Tavakoli et al., 2020). The optical properties of polymeric materials allow conventional detection practices, which suggests that hybrid devices can be a good alternative as they use the best of both materials for a sustainable pathogen detection system.

Advances in the field of diagnostics can be summarized by the following features as important characteristics for a prototype microfluidic POC device to progress to a competitive scalable product: i) Sample-to-result detection, ii) Biocompatible and assay-friendly environments, iii) Flexible device design, and iv) Automation and incorporation of artificial intelligence. The most challenging and necessary feature of such a device would be to achieve sample-to-result pathogen detection that can carry out nucleic acid extraction, reaction, signal amplification, detection, data analysis with minimal manual steps and long shelf life (Chu et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020a; T. Nguyen et al., 2020; Paul et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2019). Future scope may involve designing assays with no need for sample pre-treatment and directly using raw clinical specimens for detection. Prospects in developing diagnostics may involve applying conventional molecular methods in assay-friendly and biocompatible microfluidic environments for advanced applications. The use of agarose and polyacrylamide in microfluidic LAMP has shown the potential for these biocompatible gels in minimizing contamination challenges and delivering reagents while maintaining the performance of the assay (Chen et al., 2017). The ideal POC device can be customized for various applications and can be multiplexed to identify different relevant pathogens, depending on the specific needs of industry. Clinical applications may focus on higher assay resolution and automation while routine industrial applications (local environment testing) may prefer ease-of-use and cost effectiveness. The flexibility of a device to work across a broad range of applications would be of interest in the future. Recent global events due to Covid-19 have shifted the goal of a POC system from being principally of use in laboratory-friendly disease detection to providing a fully automated, error-free, patient-side device that has the characteristics of a smart diagnostic. The future is likely to involve the development of automated systems that can provide and analyze information to aid strategies for treatment, control, and surveillance of infectious diseases.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Funding that has been provided by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme (Grant Agreement No. 956097), and by Science Foundation Ireland (Grant No. 16/RC/3872) is gratefully acknowledged.

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